

Tenured Professional Licensed Teachers in Private Schools: An Exploratory Study

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Abstract:

This study focused on the primary motivations of tenured, professionally licensed teachers who chose and remained in private schools in Bacolod City. The research employed a qualitative method with an exploratory design. The study used semi-structured interviews as the primary research instrument to explore the experiences and motivations of selected eight tenured licensed teachers who have stayed in private schools for at least ten years. The responses aim to inspire other educators to consider teaching in private schools and provide insight into their profession. The study generated five themes with subthemes: (1) Professional Development and Growth with subthemes of Continuing Learning and Skill Enhancement (2) Sense of Belonging and Supportive Community with subthemes of Relationship Building and Collaborative Environment (3) Commitment to Quality Education and Mission with subtheme of Personal Belief (4) Teacher Recognition and Job Satisfaction with sub-themes of Student Appreciation, Service Awards, and Joys of Teaching (5) Resources and Benefits with subthemes of Teaching Materials and Technology and Benefits Packages. The researcher reflected on these themes for tenured licensed teachers who stayed in private schools for a decade or more. The investigation uncovered diverse factors that influence the retention of educators in private institutions. The analysis revealed promising signs that may influence teacher's stay in private schools. Moreover, teachers were intrinsically motivated to work, driven by their passion for teaching.

Keywords: Licensed teacher, Private school, Professional, Tenured

INTRODUCTION

The pandemic years disrupted the challenge of keeping great teachers, especially in private schools. Even before the global outbreak of coronavirus, teacher turnover rate in private institutions has been a concerning issue. Most teachers who work in private schools leave quickly after gaining experience, especially if they plan to work in public schools. These educators leave private schools even before the end of the academic year after receiving an item from the Department of Education (DepEd). Students are affected by teachers leaving private schools at any time, and administrators face a problematic situation.

Furthermore, teachers leaving private schools may not only affect the private institutions but could also impact the education landscape in the country. Solano (2024) cited that teacher shortage ranked first as a negative implication of teacher turnover. School administrators and lawmakers find the elevated teacher turnover rate alarming to the integrity of the nation's education system.

However, a previous study revealed that some educators opt to stay in private schools due to the potential advantages offered, personal development, and feelings of satisfaction. The workplace has become a harmonious individual connection (Cardino & Naparan, 2024). In addition, there are positive implications of teachers staying in private schools. Private school educators greatly influenced private schools in providing quality education to their students. These teachers helped students improve academically and prepare for their selected careers (Karbownik, 2020).

While teachers remaining in private institutions may benefit them, this may present drawbacks for public schools. If more experienced educators teach in private schools, the existing educational gap between public and private schools in the Philippines may worsen. The disparity could affect student achievement and access to quality education.

On the contrary, private school teachers' workloads are higher than public school teachers (What Characterizes Private Schools, 2024). Teachers in private schools are not exempt from facing different challenges. However, some have already been working in the private sector for years. Despite the challenges they face, they may have varied reasons for choosing to stay in private institutions.

Thus, this study explored the professional journeys of tenured licensed teachers in private schools in Bacolod City. Furthermore, it aimed to shed light on the varied aspects of their jobs by investigating their experiences and motivations and providing insights into the dynamics of teaching in private educational settings and why they chose and remained in private schools for at least ten years and more.

The researcher conducted this investigation because no similar studies are available in Bacolod City. This study will benefit people in the private sector, particularly private school administrators, principals, instructors, teacher training institutions, education policymakers, and future researchers.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Generally, this study examined the life of tenured professional licensed teachers in private schools in Bacolod City. Specifically, the study aimed to identify the primary motivations for tenured professional licensed teachers who choose and remain in private schools.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This thesis explores the motivations behind tenured professional licensed teachers who have chosen to remain in private schools for at least ten years. The theoretical framework of this study was the Two-Factor Theory of Motivation. In 1959, a behavioral scientist, Frederick Herzberg, proposed a two-factor or motivator-hygiene theory. According to Herzberg, some job factors result in satisfaction, while others prevent dissatisfaction (Herzberg, 2024).

Herzberg's theory can provide insights into factors contributing to the job satisfaction and dissatisfaction of tenured licensed teachers in private schools. Tenured teachers may value positions that give them a sense of responsibility and independence in decision-making, like curriculum development, mentorship, or leadership roles. Additionally, educators feel motivated and fulfilled when their efforts and successes in the school community are recognized.

Psychologist Abraham Maslow initially proposed the idea of a hierarchy of needs in his book in 1943. According to Maslow's hierarchy of requirements, the basic needs of employees must be addressed first before attempting to boost their motivation, passion, and involvement. Maslow refers to these needs as 'hygiene factors,' which include relationships with co-workers, workplace conditions, and organizational ideals and procedures.

Herzberg researched hygiene factors, discovering that job satisfaction and dissatisfaction almost always resulted from separate variables rather than just opposing reactions to the same factors, as previously assumed.

Like Maslow, Herzberg believes hygiene is the foundation to motivate practical efforts. However, Herzberg demonstrated that these hygiene factors or demands were more fundamental and inextricably tied to our happiness.

Hygiene factors are at the base of the pyramid. They are insufficient to inspire when used alone. When satisfied, they support the pyramid; when injured, things become unstable or, in the case of encouraging employees, ineffective (Saul, 2020).

The Two-Factor Theory concerning tenured licensed professional teachers investigates how motivators and hygiene factors affect job satisfaction and overall motivation. By identifying and addressing these aspects, educational institutions can better understand the teachers' needs and develop environments that promote more happiness, engagement, and effectiveness.

METHODS

Research Design

The researcher used a qualitative exploratory approach to determine the motivations of Tenured Professional Licensed Teachers in Private Schools. Non-numerical data was collected and analysed to better understand concepts, opinions, or experiences. In addition, qualitative research can be used to gain an in-depth understanding of a topic (Bhandari, 2020).

Participants and Sample of the Study

The study participants comprised eight (8) selected tenured professional licensed teachers in private schools in Bacolod City. Two male teachers and six females participated in this study. Purposive sampling (judgmental sampling) is a non-probability method for collecting a sample in which researchers utilize their knowledge to select participants who will assist the study in achieving its objectives (Frost, 2023).

In selecting the participants, the researcher used Purposive sampling. In employing this sampling technique, the chosen participants followed the inclusion criteria.

1. Male or female teachers teaching at present in private schools in Bacolod City who have been teaching therein for a minimum of ten (10) years and

2. Licensed professional teachers for at least five (5) years as recognized by the Philippine Regulatory Commission (PRC)

Data Gathering Tools

The researcher employed semi-structured interviews to gather the necessary information and essential data and address the problem statement. As George (2022) stated, a semi-structured interview is a method for gathering data that involves posing questions within a predefined thematic structure.

After securing the study's approval, the researcher prepared a permission letter for the key informant or participant. After securing permission, the researcher personally identified and interviewed the key informants of the study. The interview was conducted during the participants' vacant schedule and free time to avoid distraction from their work and to give them enough time to answer the questions. After data gathering, the researcher transcribed the interview and identified the codes and themes used for the data analysis. Lastly, the researcher safeguarded the recorded, written, and audio interviews.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher obtained the participants' consent by sending a communication letter about the interview to the private school teachers involved in the study. Additionally, the researcher clarified the study's objective to the participants. She discussed ethical considerations for their confidentiality. The researcher emphasized how the data will be protected and stored securely. After obtaining all the necessary consents, the researcher contacted the participants to agree on the interview date. Additionally, the researcher asked for the participants' permission to have the interview session audiotaped.

During the interview, the researcher encouraged the participants to freely recall and share their experiences in any way they believed to be helpful. Throughout the interview, the researcher keenly observed the participants' gestures for hints of confusion. In this way, the researcher must revise a question to make it more transparent and interesting.

After the interviews, the researcher analyzed and interpreted the data to answer the problem and reach a valid conclusion.

Data Analysis Procedure

The researcher employed a thematic analysis originally developed by Virginia Braun and Victoria Clarke to examine the data. It usually refers to a collection of texts, such as an interview or transcripts. The researcher attentively studied the data to uncover common themes, subjects, concepts, and patterns of meaning that come up repeatedly. The thematic analysis consists of six stages: (1) familiarize with the data; (2) generate initial codes; (3) formulate and merge codes into themes; (4) review themes; (5) specify and name themes; and (6) generate the report.

Data Trustworthiness

To establish the trustworthiness of a qualitative study, the researcher addressed the four criteria of credibility, confirmability, dependability, and transferability. The researcher used different techniques to ensure the findings were reliable, valid, and applicable to other contexts.

The researcher took measures to enhance the credibility of the findings by minimizing bias and increasing accuracy. The researcher used member checking, involving the distribution of transcripts and summaries to the participants, to ensure the accuracy of qualitative findings. The participants examined the information and gave the researcher feedback regarding discrepancies, inaccuracies, or absent data. This method aids in establishing credibility and builds trust between the researcher and the participants. In addition, member checking allows participants to clarify or expand on their experiences, potentially increasing the richness and depth of the data (Sago, 2023).

Specifically, the researcher sent a letter along with the synthesized member checking (SMC) report adopted from the proposed member checking process. The document provided a section wherein they may provide comments on the interpretation made by the researcher.

The researcher also guaranteed the confirmability of the study results. Statistics Solutions (2019) indicates that confirmability guarantees that the findings are influenced by the participants and not by the qualitative researcher. This standard pertains to the reliability of the research study's findings derived from the narratives and words of participants, instead of any possible researcher biases.

The audit trail kept in this study included an audio recording of the interview, interview transcripts, a record of unique topics, notes, thoughts on coding, and the meaning of themes. The researcher documented the process of data collection, analysis, and interpretation.

Dependability (consistency) is one of the four criteria for rigor and trustworthiness in qualitative research (Janis, 2022). To ensure the data's dependability, the researcher established an acceptable degree to which the study's findings were consistent over time and across different researchers. Dependability in qualitative research is associated with reliability. It measures the extent to which a research study repeated by a separate researcher yields the same results. Dependability is all about the depth of the research procedure (Trustworthiness in Qualitative Research, 2022).

The researcher used the Perfect Agreement intercoder reliability test in this study. Intercoder reliability measures how frequently two or more coders code similarly. It ensures that coders agree on the exact definition of the coding system and not on a single person's opinion (Reisner, 2023). An external auditor listened to the audiotaped interviews to establish the reliability of the coding. The external auditor, the independent coder, evaluated the codes prepared by the researcher to demonstrate agreement with the coding. The researcher served as coder one (1), while the independent coder was coder two (2). The value of 1 was assigned to the code when the independent coder agreed, and 0 (zero) if disagreed. Since the code prepared by the researcher will be the basis for evaluating the coding agreement, all the researcher's codes will be rated 1. The researcher established a value of 96.55 percent agreement, indicating a complete level of agreement. Consequently, the findings of this study demonstrated outstanding reliability.

Finally, the researcher validated the study's transferability through investigation. Through purposive sampling, the researcher ensured that the findings would apply to different contexts or groups. The researcher outlined the criteria for choosing the participants and adequately explained them and the study's setting.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher secured the participants' informed consent while ensuring their anonymity and the confidentiality of the information. Additionally, this research initiative noted the disposal of data. The researcher clarified the study's rationale and objectives to the participants. Furthermore, each participant received an informed consent form, which made the teachers' participation voluntary.

This study did not use the participants' real names; instead, they were individually identified throughout this paper using a code, such as P1 for participant 1, to address the participants' anonymity. Data confidentiality was essential to this research, especially when handling sensitive data. The information was kept confidential and safeguarded against authorized access, usage, disclosure, or destruction beyond the research setting.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thematic Findings

The study aimed to identify the primary motivations of tenured professional licensed teachers working in private schools in Bacolod City. Five themes with sub-themes emerged from the thematic analysis of participants' responses based on their experiences teaching in private schools.

THEME 1: Professional Development and Growth

Educators in private institutions prioritize professional development, growth, and career progression. They wish to acquire knowledge and advance, emphasizing the significance of progress in their selected professions. Educators view private schools as opportunities for ongoing skill and knowledge enhancement.

According to Agarwal (2024), professional development provides teachers with the most recent knowledge and skills. Whether incorporating technology into the classroom, introducing new curriculum standards, or addressing students' different learning styles, professional development for teachers ensures that they stay at the forefront of their practice. Teachers need to be versatile, especially in the age of technology. Private schools send their teachers for seminars, training, or workshops for free. Private schools allot a portion of their budget for the professional development of their teachers. Even in the classroom, teachers can practice using technology in class or a simple activity on different learning styles. The world of education is evolving. New technologies have developed, and educators must stay current. Additionally, Agarwal (2024) highlighted the advantages of professional development, which can enable and improve teachers.

Fareed (2021) emphasized that educators should participate in ongoing professional development to stay updated with fresh concepts. Numerous institutions emphasize enhancing students' interpersonal abilities and

soft skills, which are unfamiliar to the teaching staff. Teachers must improve their ability to analyze, study, and share knowledge with their pupils.

Under this first theme, two (2) subthemes emerged: (1) Continuous Learning and (2) Skill Enhancement.

1.1. Continuous Learning

Continuous learning is self-motivated persistence in obtaining knowledge and competencies to broaden one's skill set and pursue new opportunities. It is part of one's personal and professional development to prevent stagnation and reach one's potential (Seven Reasons Why Continuous Learning Is Important | Edexec, 2020).

Teachers recognize that learning is a lifelong pursuit. They seek additional education to acquire knowledge, maintain motivation, and stay competitive. Furthermore, it serves as a means for them to stay informed about educational trends and improve their effectiveness as teachers.

1.2. Skill Enhancement

Skill enhancement focuses on the development of specific skills. Private schools allow educators to participate in seminars, webinars, workshops, and training sessions. Improving their skills, such as managing a classroom and integrating technology, is crucial. Additionally, acquiring these skills enables teachers to excel in their profession.

During the interview, three teachers said,

"Many things convinced me to stay in private school. Number one, as I have experienced myself, my school supported me in my professional growth, that's one, and it nurtured me as a teacher. Then, they send me to seminars and give me opportunities to grow professionally." (P2)

"After 24 years of teaching in a private school, I realized that one factor is the learning opportunities. There are many opportunities in private schools that can help us grow professionally. As teachers, we don't stop our learning right there. We need to develop more professionally, so that is one significant factor." (P1)

Then, of course, we also need to take master's studies because learning is never-ending, and we need to update ourselves with current trends to continue to exist and become relevant." (P6)

According to the article "The Importance of Professional Development for Teachers" (2022), educational needs and the wider world are constantly changing, so Continuous Professional Development is essential. CPD gives teachers the techniques and expertise to keep up with these changing times.

THEME 2: Sense of Belonging and Supportive Community

Teachers find a reason to remain in private schools because of the supportive community, which creates a sense of belonging. They feel they are valued, leading to greater job satisfaction.

Belonging means valued, loved, and respected for who we are. The same is true in the workplace. Employee engagement is a key result of diversity, equity, and inclusion strategies. Belonging goes beyond personal fulfillment and is vital to an organization's success. According to extensive research, belonging affects mental, physical, and social well-being (Bennett, 2024).

Similarly, a sense of belonging is from an innate desire to interact with others. The basic need for acceptance, belonging, and social interaction is human nature's core (Allen et al., 2021). In education, a teacher who enjoys positive interactions with colleagues and the school community is more likely to experience long-term fulfillment and a strong sense of belonging, leading to a greater likelihood of staying in that institution. In addition, having a healthy working environment is equated to a supportive community where everyone feels a sense of belonging. It was one of the results of a study on why teachers continue working in private schools (Cardino & Naparan, 2024). Colleagues and administrators need to recognize teachers' contributions so they feel valued and appreciated. Giving teachers a voice in school decisions is a way of making them feel part of the community. Creating a supportive environment is essential in building a strong culture for teacher retention.

Under this second theme, two (2) subthemes emerged: (1) Relationship Building and (2) Collaborative Environment.

2.1. Relationship Building

Teachers who invest in strong relationships in private schools are likely to stay. The nurturing environment among colleagues and students contributes to a fulfilling work experience. The camaraderie of the teachers creates a strong bond so that they do not feel separated from the school.

2.2. Collaborative Environment

Educators appreciate the positive work environment found in private schools. It has a supportive leadership team from the administrators and a collaborative culture among colleagues and school staff with a shared purpose.

Interviewed teachers revealed:

"The number one factor that affected my decision to stay in a private school was the kind of community in which I belonged. I am happy where I am right now, so I am more than motivated to continue teaching in a private school." (P3)

"Staying in a private school gave me a positive work environment compared to public school. In public school, my health was not good. I was able to teach in private rather than in public school. After 12 years in private school, I transferred to public school, and then I realized that my health was not fit in that environment, so I would rather go back to my old school, which fortunately was able to accept me back." (P5)

"And also, the sisters (nuns), the parents are very supportive, and the whole community itself." (P6)

"One that made me stay is the community, clientele, and environment relationship. The thought is that the community is always there to support and to give or boost the morale of the teachers and the programs they prepare for us." (P7)

"I think the sense of being welcomed and accepted in the community, or the sense of belongingness, so to speak. I have also felt that this supportive community and the ability to foster friendly relationships with the teachers, students, and parents create a fulfilling teaching experience for twenty-four years and counting." (P8)

Team (2023) pointed out that the third level of Maslow's hierarchy of needs is love and belongingness. Humans need to give and receive love to feel like they belong in a group. Individuals may experience loneliness or depression when deprived of these needs. Private school teachers feel comfortable in a collaborative environment where everyone supports each other. When cooperation is evident, tasks become easy, no matter how hard they are. They feel a sense of belonging when colleagues resonate with what they give. It gives a reason for the teachers to stay in private schools.

THEME 3: Commitment to Quality Education and Mission

Auld (2023) defines quality education as the key to a healthy and prosperous life. The United Nations (UN) 17 Sustainable Development Goals indicate that education is the key to escaping poverty. In their 2030 Sustainable Agenda for Sustainable Development, the UN commits to providing inclusive and equitable quality education at all times. Quality teachers are significant to quality education.

On the other hand, teachers can benefit from school mission and vision statements regarding their relationships with fellow teachers and students since the common language and purpose of the statements provide common ground for those relationships (Marymount University, 2023). Given the passion to teach, educators are committed to aligning themselves with the school's mission. As a result, this serves as a motivation for them to stay in the institution.

Private schools typically offer quality education and have a clear mission and vision for their clientele. In the same way, teachers are highly motivated, with a sense of purpose that makes them feel connected to the institution and want to contribute to its success. Teachers feel proud of being able to help, which gives them a reason to stay in their school.

Under the third theme, one (1) subtheme emerged: (1) Personal Belief.

3.1. Personal Belief

This subtheme is essential for understanding the elements affecting teachers' choice to stay in private schools. The declaration reflects the teacher's values, convictions, and organizational commitment. Teachers prefer a school environment that aligns with their personal beliefs. This subtheme significantly influences educators' teaching in Catholic schools.

Three teachers pointed out during the interviews:

"I chose to teach in the private institution due to the alignment of the school's vision and mission with my personal beliefs, especially with the educative community." (P8)

"I think it's the spiritual formation that the school has been giving us, the retreats, recollections, masses, and the like." (P3)

"Again, the quality education offered by the school is vital. That's why being a part of the institution or the school that offers quality education to the clientele is an inspiration to stay where I am right now. You just got to be within the system, you got to love and believe the vision-mission of the school, and then you go to work with whatever is best for the students." (P2)

According to Auld (2023), effective teaching is vital for quality education. Exceptional educators are the fundamental element of quality education. Educators consider each student's spiritual, social, emotional, mental, physical, and cognitive growth. The goal is to nurture each student's inherent character, skills, and interests, equipping them for a life of purposeful contribution in their work, home, and community activities. Quality teachers are needed to have a quality education.

Meanwhile, a study by Nelson & Yang (2022) examined teachers' attitudes toward and responses to religious diversity in the classroom and the relationship between their beliefs, previous experience, and professional behavior. All teachers surveyed indicated that their religious beliefs significantly influenced the methods they applied to address classroom diversity challenges. It suggests that teachers' beliefs influence how they handle classroom matters.

TSV Catholic Education (2024) asserts that teachers' understanding of Church teachings, the Catholic faith tradition, Gospel values, and their role in the Church's mission is essential to developing students' critical thinking skills, which help them discern between what is good and faithful and what is not. Private Catholic schools prefer Catholic teacher applicants. Teachers have imbibed the teachings and ways of the Church because they practiced these things in a school setting. Some teachers have strengthened their faith because of the religious activities in Catholic schools.

THEME 4: Teacher Recognition and Job Satisfaction

Recognition significantly impacts motivation, teachers' emotions, and their performance. Hodges (2024) states teachers who receive regular recognition are productive and engaged at work. They are more likely to receive higher satisfaction scores from students and parents. Above all, they are more likely to stay with their school.

Recognizing the teachers' efforts in varied ways is rewarding and fulfilling for them. It enhances and motivates them to do better, which leads to job satisfaction. These teachers are most likely to stay in a private school setting if they feel valued as people and for their service.

Meanwhile, it is worth noting the definition of teachers' job satisfaction as teachers' emotional reactions to their jobs or teaching roles (Özkan, U. B., & Akgenc, 2022).

Under the fourth theme, two (3) subthemes emerged: (1) Student Appreciation, (2) Service Awards, and (3) Joys of Teaching.

4.1. Student Appreciation

Students show gratitude to their teachers for their success. They return to their school and acknowledge what their teachers have done to them, contributing to their current status in life. Recognizing teachers' efforts is a joy for them. It gives them a satisfying feeling and the need to continue to serve the school.

4.2. Service Awards

The school recognizes teachers who have shown loyalty over the past years. In most private schools, the service award honors those who have served the institution for five years, ten years, and so on. Every year, the private schools recognize the service awardees by giving them a plaque of appreciation and cash incentives to the recipients through a program and a gathering. Teachers are motivated to stay in the institution for this benefit.

4.3. Joys of Teaching

Teachers are satisfied with their jobs, which is evident in their faces. Unsure of how much they can get at the end of the month, for them, there is joy in teaching. It is a noble profession. Teachers do not expect to become rich in this profession but are willing to share their talents and skills, and what they can give or contribute to their students. They are looking after the lifelong skills of their students and how these students can have bright futures and contribute to shaping our society.

Interviewed teachers revealed:

"When I get to be appreciated by students, every time I meet students outside the school, they would greet me, and they would tell me things that they remember about me." (P1)

"I am happy where I am right now, so I am more than motivated to continue teaching in a private school. Simple encounters with the students and the graders, day-to-day conversations with them, and the simple hugs they give me bring a sense of fulfillment as a teacher in a private school. (P3)

"Yes, fifteen, twenty, twenty-five. For twenty-five years of service, you receive another award, and that is the Medrano Award. Medrano is our school's first lay partner. So, it was honored after him, and you received an extra gift besides the one you will receive for your years of service." (P4)

According to Hoque et al. (2023), teachers' job satisfaction substantially impacts their lessons since they directly impart knowledge to students. Teachers are essential in delivering the lessons to their students. If they are contented, there is a positive feeling that will eventually create a positive environment and relationship with the students. Job satisfaction has a significant impact on why teachers remain in their workplace.

THEME 5: Resources and Benefits

Faculty members who stayed in private schools for many years claimed they liked the school because of its resources and attractive employee benefits. The salary may not be that big, but it could finance the family's needs. They expressed their commitment to the institution because they felt they were cared for. With these, they do not plan to move or transfer to a public school.

Under the fifth theme, two (2) subthemes emerged: (1) Teaching Materials and Technology and (2) Benefit Packages.

5.1. Teaching Materials and Technology

Private school teachers are motivated to deliver their lessons in innovative ways. The instructional materials are readily available without spending money to buy them. The school facilities are also a good reason for teachers to stay in their workplace. Life is easy when it comes to their needs in teaching. As with the changing times, teachers in private schools are also lucky to enjoy the technology. Classrooms are air-conditioned and equipped with smart TVs, which make the place conducive for learning. This kind of environment is in contrast with the public schools.

5.2. Benefit Packages

Tenured teachers also enjoy benefit packages from the school. The longer one stays in a private school, the more benefits one can get. Benefit Packages come in different forms, from healthcare to bonuses. Teachers are grateful to the school, especially if qualified to receive educational benefits for their children. What is good about this benefit is that the children of the teachers can avail themselves of the free tuition fees up to college, which is one reason teachers stay in private schools.

Teachers highlighted:

"We have health care benefits, we have an HMO, we also have 13th month, we also have celebrations for Teacher's Day. I think that's the basic thing that the private school can offer." (P5)

"Well, of course, in private school, we have the facilities, the students, the community, and the ambiance, and of course, I can easily blend with the people around me." (P6)

Inadequate school facilities affect teacher performance (Three Effects School Facilities Have on Academic Achievement, n.d.) A well-built facility will create a safe working environment for educators and pupils and encourage teachers to join and stay on the teaching staff. Proper facilities provide teachers and children with a safe learning environment that is also good for their physical and emotional well-being. Private schools have good facilities, which entice teachers to stay.

On the other hand, Indeed (2021) emphasized that benefits assist employees in paying for insurance, saving for retirement, and taking time from work when needed. Knowing the value of benefits packages can help managers provide more comprehensive packages to attract and retain outstanding people and assist employees and applicants in determining their roles' priorities.

Meanwhile, Employee Benefits Design to Attract and Retain Talent (2022) states that employees with the best benefits tend to be the most loyal. The more diverse the health, risk protection, and well-being benefits available, the more employees feel valued by their business. As a result, they feel more invigorated and are less likely to leave. Teachers are attracted to the benefits but pointed out that this was not the only reason they were motivated to stay in private institutions.

The results generally emphasize how crucial professional ethics and qualities are for teachers working in private schools. The themes suggested that while private schools shared some standard features that contributed to job satisfaction, there were also unique aspects based on individual school cultures, missions, and resources. Regardless

of these disparities, supportive work settings, opportunities for career advancement, and positive relationships greatly impacted teachers' decisions to remain in private schools.

Nonetheless, the results had significant implications for policymakers, school leaders, and administrators of private institutions concerning teachers' motivations. When examining tenured professional licensed teachers in private schools, Frederick Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory of Motivation is essential. The generated themes revealed some motivations mentioned in the study that resulted in teachers' decision to stay in private schools.

On the other hand, Abraham Maslow's third hierarchy of needs, which includes the sense of belonging and love, motivated teachers to remain in private school settings. The need for a sense of belonging affects private school educators when choosing a positive work environment. It is not just about the benefits or opportunities, but finding a place where they feel valued, connected, and aligned with the school's mission.

Fig. 1. Simulacrum Diagram

The figure above shows the simulacrum diagram of the study's flow. Tenured professional licensed teachers participated in the study, and their motivations were determined through semi-structured interviews. The results of the study will provide insights into the dynamics of teaching in private educational settings.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The research results concluded that tenured professional licensed educators possess varying reasons for staying in private schools. While other codes were standard to most teachers, surprising codes emerged based on the participants' responses. Staying in One's Comfort Zone implies that familiarity and belonging may occasionally serve as powerful motivators than pursuing new opportunities. The participant mentioned that he feels comfortable and at home in the current private school, showing hesitation to step out of his "comfort zone." The idea contrasts with the common perception of teachers seeking new opportunities.

Conversely, the code Impact over Income indicated that certain educators valued the influence they could exert on students more than monetary rewards, a crucial element in many careers. The code emphasized the commitment and enthusiasm of educators to instruct in private institutions. Indeed, teaching is a noble profession for these teachers. Private school teachers emphasized how vital commitment is in their chosen field. Commitment to quality education, professional growth and development, teacher recognition, and mission contributed to a supportive teacher environment. Additionally, the research emphasized the significance of work ethics for educators in private schools, demonstrating a positive connection between these qualities and commitment and job satisfaction.

This research offers valuable insights for both private schools and educational leaders. By understanding the motivations that contribute to teachers' decision to remain in private institutions, schools can prioritize and cultivate a positive and supportive work environment.

Recommendations

The following are recommendations to different stakeholders based on the results and conclusions of the study.

School administrators, heads, and leaders can continue to support professional development and provide opportunities to enhance teacher skills and knowledge. They can allocate a budget that caters to the needs of tenured teachers to finance training, conferences, and workshops specifically designed for experienced teachers to address current educational issues. Tenured teachers can be involved in decision-making, such as curriculum development, school improvement, or policy changes. Furthermore, heads, school administrators, and leaders can develop a mentoring program where tenured professors guide the novices by sharing their expertise. In addition, administrators may assign leadership roles to long-term teachers. Moreover, leaders can establish a mechanism for regularly recognizing teacher contributions and accomplishments, therefore appreciating their efforts and impact on the students' lives.

Private School Teachers can improve their skills, acquire new techniques, remain updated on educational developments, engage in collaborative activities, share effective strategies, convey their needs and concerns to school leaders, and support policies and resources that foster their professional advancement and overall well-being.

Teacher Training Institutions can better equip aspiring teachers with the knowledge and skills to navigate their careers effectively by training and including exercises on building positive relationships with colleagues, administrators, and the community.

Future researchers may use the study's results to enrich our understanding of the teaching profession, focusing on private school teachers, inform future research inquiries, and guide policy and practice in education.

While this study has produced significant findings, it primarily concentrated on tenured professional licensed educators in private institutions in Bacolod City. Researchers can also examine professional educators who stay in public schools for at least ten years. This comparative analysis will reveal similarities and distinctions in different areas of both sectors.

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